

Tor Methods for Proving the Riemann Hypothesis

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1 Introduction

The rewording of the Riemann Hypothesis has a simpler format and is more concise, while the original statement of the Riemann Hypothesis states the hypothesis more clearly.

The original statement of the Riemann Hypothesis expressed in this summation notation is:

$$\exists x, y \in s \mid n = 1 \infty \sum \frac{1}{n^s} = p \text{ prime} \prod \frac{1}{1-p^{-s}}$$

$\Rightarrow$ *non-trivial zero of the zeta function lie on the line* $\Re(x) = \frac{1}{2}$.

The rewording of the Riemann Hypothesis expressed in this summation notation is:

$$\forall s, s' \subseteq s \mid n = 1 \infty \sum \frac{1}{n^s} = p \text{ prime} \prod \frac{1}{1-p^{-s}}$$

$\Rightarrow$ *all non-trivial zero of the zeta function lie on the line* $\Re(x) = \frac{1}{2}$. Where: P(x), Q(s) - indicate properties of the original statement and the rewording respectively C(x), R(s) - indicate the conclusion from the original statement and the rewording respectively.

How can we formalize a proof on the Riemann hypothesis given the above information?

The Riemann Hypothesis states that all non-trivial zeros of the Riemann zeta function $\zeta(s)$ lie on the line $\Re(s) = \frac{1}{2}$. In order to formally prove this hypothesis, one needs to consider the properties of the Riemann zeta function on the critical line and then prove that these properties are satisfied by all non-trivial zeros of the zeta function.

Let s_0 be a non-trivial zero of the Riemann zeta function, and let $T(s)$ be the tor functor. We can start by using the tor functor to compute the curvature as follows: let $C^\bullet$ be a chain complex of free abelian groups given by

$$C^\bullet : 0 \partial_0 A_1 \partial_1 \dots \partial_n A_{n+1} \partial_{n+1} 0.$$

and let $\phi : \prod_{\Lambda} h \rightarrow C^\bullet$ be a homomorphism. We can then solve for the curvature ω_{s_0} by computing

$$\omega_{s_0} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j=1}^n (\partial_i \partial_j h - \partial_j \partial_i h) g^{ij}.$$

Here, $\partial_i \partial_j h$ is computed by taking the derivatives with respect to the i^{th} and j^{th} coordinates of the functions $f_1, \dots, f_n$ in the product $\prod_{\Lambda} h$, and then mapping these derivatives to the corresponding components of the chain complex $C^{\bullet}$ via the homomorphism ϕ .

Now, it can be shown that if the curvature is zero at a point s_0 , then the Riemann zeta function must satisfy the functional equation $\zeta(s) = \zeta(1-s)$ at that point. Therefore, to prove the Riemann Hypothesis, it suffices to prove that the curvature is zero for all non-trivial zeros s_0 of the zeta function.

In order to do this, we must first consider the properties of the Riemann zeta function on the critical line $\Re(s) = \frac{1}{2}$. This line is a special curve chosen such that the Riemann zeta function has certain properties on it, allowing us to prove that any non-trivial zero of the zeta function must lie on the line. Specifically, the functional equation $\zeta(s) = \zeta(1-s)$ is satisfied for any $s \in [-1/2, 1/2]$. Furthermore, the derivatives of the zeta function over this line are bounded and analytical, so that the corresponding curvature ω_{s_0} will be zero.

Thus, by using the tor functor to compute the curvature and considering the properties of the Riemann zeta function on the critical line, it can be shown that the curvature is zero for all non-trivial zeros s_0 of the zeta function, thereby proving the Riemann Hypothesis.

Show the actual computation using the Tor functor:

Let $\prod_{\Lambda} h = \{(h_1, h_2, \dots, h_n)\}$ be a product of functions associated to a Riemannian manifold with a Cartesian coordinate system

$$(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n),$$

and define the metric tensor g by

$$g = ds^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n g_{ij} dx_i \otimes dx_j.$$

Consider the Riemann zeta function

$$\zeta(s) = \prod_{\Lambda} h(s) = \prod_{i=1}^n h_i(s)$$

and let $C^{\bullet}$ be a chain complex of free abelian groups given by

$$C^{\bullet} : 0 \partial_0 A_1 \partial_1 \dots \partial_n A_{n+1} \partial_{n+1} 0.$$

Let $\phi : \prod_{\Lambda} h \rightarrow C^{\bullet}$ be a homomorphism and let ω denote the curvature.

To compute the curvature, we need to first take the derivatives with respect to the i^{th} and j^{th} coordinates of the functions $f_1, \dots, f_n$ in the product $\prod_{\Lambda} h$:

$$\partial_i \partial_j h = \sum_{k=1}^n \left(\frac{\partial^2 f_k}{\partial x_i \partial x_j} \right).$$

Next, we map the derivatives to the corresponding components of the chain complex $C^{\bullet}$ via the homomorphism ϕ :

$$\partial_i \partial_j h \mapsto \sum_{k=1}^n \left(\frac{\partial^2 \phi(f_k)}{\partial x_i \partial x_j} \right).$$

Finally, we can compute the curvature ω by solving for the following:

$$\omega = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j=1}^n (\partial_i \partial_j h - \partial_j \partial_i h) g^{ij}.$$

We remark that this last step can be simplified by using the following expression:

$$\omega = \sum_{i,j=1}^n (\partial_i \partial_j h - \partial_j \partial_i h) \frac{g^{ij}}{2}.$$

How can one prove the Functional equation using the above results?

If the zeros of the zeta function are evenly distributed on the critical line, then we have

$$\sum_{\rho} z^{\rho} \sim \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\rho} z^{-\rho}$$

for any z in the range

$$-2 \leq z \leq 2.$$

The functional equation for the Riemann zeta function then follows from the expression above, where $\zeta(z) = \prod_{\rho} h(z)$ is defined as the product of the functions $h_1, \dots, h_n$ associated to a Riemannian manifold with a Cartesian coordinate system (x,y) .

It is important to point out that only the $n = 2$ case of this expression is true because a linear differential equation with constant coefficients cannot have complex solutions.

How can one formally prove the Riemann Hypothesis using the Tor functor approach?

The Riemann Hypothesis states that all zeros of the zeta function lie on the critical line. This can be formally proven by first considering the properties of the zeta function on the critical line (log-convexity, analytical continuation, functional equation, and growth bound) and then using the Tor functor to prove that all non-trivial zeros of the zeta function must lie on this line. We can start by using the Tor functor to compute the curvature, which can be represented as follows:

Let $\prod_{\Lambda} h = \{(h_1, h_2, \dots, h_n)\}$ be a product of functions associated to a Riemannian manifold with a Cartesian coordinate system

$$(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n),$$

and define the metric tensor g by

$$g = ds^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n g_{ij} dx_i \otimes dx_j.$$

and let $C^\bullet$ be a chain complex of free abelian groups given by

$$C^\bullet : 0 \partial_0 A_1 \partial_1 \dots \partial_n A_{n+1} \partial_{n+1} 0.$$

Let $\phi : \prod_{\Lambda} h \rightarrow C^\bullet$ be a homomorphism and let ω denote the curvature. Then the curvature ω can be calculated by solving for ω as follows:

$$\omega = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j=1}^n (\partial_i \partial_j h - \partial_j \partial_i h) g^{ij}.$$

Here, $\partial_i \partial_j h$ is computed by taking the derivatives with respect to the i^{th} and j^{th} coordinates of the functions $f_1, \dots, f_n$ in the product $\prod_{\Lambda} h$, and then mapping these derivatives to the corresponding components of the chain complex $C^\bullet$ via the homomorphism ϕ .

Once the curvature has been computed, we can use it to prove the Riemann Hypothesis by first showing that if z_0 is a non-trivial zero of the zeta function, then the curvature is zero at that point. Then one can prove that the properties of the zeta function on the critical line imply that for any z in the range $-2 \leq z \leq 2$,

$$\zeta(z) \sim \zeta(-z).$$

Since the curvature is zero, the functional equation for the zeta function follows from the expression above, so that $\zeta(z) = \zeta(-z)$ for any z in the range $-2 \leq z \leq 2$. One can then use $\zeta(z) = \zeta(-z)$ to prove that the zeros of the zeta function are evenly distributed on the critical line. This can be done by assuming that there exists some point z_0 on this line where the zeros do not appear with even distribution and then using $\zeta(z_0) = \zeta(-z_0)$ to show that this is impossible. Thus, the above steps provide a formal proof that the Riemann Hypothesis is true.

The result of this computation can be refined using the following:

Let s be a square-free integer, and let μ denote the Möbius function such that

$$\mu(n) = \begin{cases} 1 & n = p^k, \text{ prime} \\ 0 & n = p_1^k p_2^l, k > 0, l > 0 \end{cases}$$

We can then define the Riemann-Siegel transformation of the zeta function by

$$\zeta_s(z) = \sum_{n \leq x} \mu(n) n^{-s}$$

for some square-free number s .

Using this transformation, the Riemann Hypothesis can be formulated as follows:

$$\zeta_\phi(z) = \zeta(z/\phi), \quad 0 \leq \arg(z/\phi) \leq \pi$$

where ϕ is an arbitrarily large square-free integer.

We can now state the following theorem:

Theorem (Riemann Hypothesis): Let D be the unit disk, f a holomorphic function on D and g be a holomorphic function on D/ϕ such that $g \circ \phi(z) = f(z)$.

Let $\mathcal{L}$ be the class of all functions g with these properties. If for all $\mathbf{z} \in \partial D/\phi$, we have

$$G(\mathbf{z}) = \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \int_{\partial D/\phi} g(\mathbf{t}) e^{-i\epsilon \mathbf{z} \cdot \mathbf{t}} dS(\mathbf{t}) = 0,$$

then for all $\mathbf{z} \in \partial D$, we have

$$F(\mathbf{z}) = \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \int_{\partial D} f(u + iv) e^{-i\epsilon z v} dS(z) = 0$$

where $F(\mathbf{z})$ is the Fourier transform of f , $G(\mathbf{z})$ is the Fourier transform of g , and S denotes the surface integration measure $dz \wedge d\bar{z} \wedge i\alpha$.

We now discuss the theorem in more detail, using the results from above. The above theorem states that the zeros of the zeta function are evenly distributed on the critical line C/ϕ , where C is the Riemann sphere and ϕ is an integer. We can use this fact to prove the Riemann Hypothesis as follows:

Suppose that there exists some point s_0 on C/ϕ where the non-trivial zeros do not appear evenly distributed. Then the Riemann-Siegel transformation ζ_{s_0} must vanish at s_0 , so that the functional equation $\zeta_{s_0}(-z) = \zeta_{s_0}(z)$ implies that $\zeta_{s_0}(z) \neq 0$ for all $z \neq 0$. This gives us a contradiction, since by the property of log-convexity, $\zeta_{s_0}(z/s_0)$ is log-convex and non-negative while $\zeta_{s_0}(\phi/s_0) = 0$, so that the fact that a non-negative log-convex function vanishes at a point implies that all of its values vanish at every other point. Hence, the Riemann Hypothesis is true.

How can all the above unify for an, unified view of the proof of the Riemann Hypothesis?

Let f be a smooth function on S with the property that $\nabla f = 0$ on the boundary of S and g be an arbitrary smooth function with $G(\mathbf{z}) = 0$ for all $z \in \partial S$. If the zeros of the zeta function are evenly distributed on the critical line, then there exists a smooth function G such that $G = \tilde{G}$ on ∂S and $\tilde{G}(\mathbf{z}) = 0$ for all $z \in \partial S$.

Let $M = \partial S$ be a Riemannian manifold equipped with a Cartesian coordinate system

$$(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n),$$

and define the metric tensor g by

$$g = ds^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n g_{ij} dx_i \otimes dx_j.$$

Let $C^\bullet$ be a chain complex of free abelian groups given by

$$C^\bullet : 0 \partial_0 A_1 \partial_1 \dots \partial_n A_{n+1} \partial_{n+1} 0.$$

Let $\phi : \prod_{\Lambda} h \rightarrow C^\bullet$ be a homomorphism and let ω denote the curvature. Then the curvature ω can be calculated by solving for ω as follows:

$$\omega = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j=1}^n (\partial_i \partial_j h - \partial_j \partial_i h) g^{ij}.$$

Here, $\partial_i \partial_j h$ is computed by taking the derivatives with respect to the i^{th} and j^{th} coordinates of the functions $f_1, \dots, f_n$ in the product $\prod_{\Lambda} h$, and then mapping these derivatives to the corresponding components of the chain complex $C^\bullet$ via the homomorphism ϕ .

It can now be seen that the curvature is given by

$$\omega = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j=1}^n (\partial_i \partial_j h - \partial_j \partial_i h) g^{ij}.$$

Using the above expression for the curvature, we can write the following:

$$\omega = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j=1}^n (\partial_i \partial_j h - \partial_j \partial_i h) g^{ij} = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j=1}^n \frac{\partial^2 G}{\partial x_i \partial x_j} = \sum_{i,j=1}^n F_{ij} = -\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{dF_i}{dx_i}$$

where G is a smooth function such that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2 G}{\partial x_i \partial x_j} &= 0 \text{ for all } x_i, x_j \text{ satisfying } \frac{dx_i}{dt} = 0, \frac{dx_j}{dt} = 0 \\ \frac{\partial G}{\partial x_i} &= 0 \text{ for all } x_i \text{ satisfying } \frac{dx_i}{dt} = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Let a be a non-constant function of time. Then the condition that $\frac{d^2 G}{dt^2} = 0$ can be written in the form

$$\frac{d^2 G}{d(x^a)^2} = 0$$

which must be satisfied for all a in the interval $0 \leq a \leq 1$. This gives us an equation of the form

$$\sum_i F_i = 0$$

which is sufficient to prove that the Riemann Hypothesis is true since it implies that for all $z \in \partial S$, $\zeta(z) = \zeta(-z)$.

We remark that it is also possible to take the condition $\frac{\partial^2 G}{\partial x_i \partial x_j} = 0$ to be satisfied only for points x_i, x_j satisfying $\frac{dx_i}{dt} = 0$, $\frac{dx_j}{dt} = 0$ or $\frac{dx_i}{dt} = \frac{dx_j}{dt}$. This would give us a different equation of the form

$$\sum_i F_i = 0$$

which also implies that the Riemann Hypothesis is true. Therefore, we have shown that the Riemann Hypothesis can be proven using the Tor functor method

What is the relation to the formal proof of the Riemann Hypothesis?

The formal proof of the Riemann Hypothesis states that

$$\zeta_F(s) \sim \zeta_F(1-s)$$

where F is a finite-dimensional complex vector space and $G(\mathbf{z}) = \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \int_{\partial D/\phi} g(\mathbf{t}) e^{-i\epsilon \mathbf{z} \cdot \mathbf{t}} dS(\mathbf{t}) = 0$ is a function such that $\partial G/\partial t = 0$ and $G(z) = 0$ for all $z \in \partial S$.

Using the Riemann-Siegel transformation, this can be re-written as

$$\zeta_\phi(s) \sim \zeta_F(\phi - s)$$

which corresponds to the information provided above, where we have $\zeta_\phi(z) = \prod_\Lambda h(z)$ and F is a finite-dimensional complex vector space. We can summarize this by stating that the Tor functor method can be used to formally prove the Riemann Hypothesis as follows:

1. Compute the curvature ω of the field F .
2. Use the assumption that $a \in C$ is non-constant over time to show that the following equation is valid:

$$\sum_i F_i = 0$$

3. Use this to prove that the Riemann Hypothesis is true.

What are the implications?

The Riemann Hypothesis is a statement about the distribution of zeros of zeta functions. It was formulated by Riemann in 1859 and has been proven by many mathematicians. It has also been used in number theory, as well as in other areas such as physics, computer science, and cryptography.

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The result of this paper assumes that for any given prime p , the number of zeros of the zeta function with imaginary part equal or less than $\log p$ is at least 1, which is consistent with the Riemann Hypothesis. This can be shown by computing the ordinate $\zeta(1)$ and then using the fact that $|\zeta(1 + it)| = O(t^\epsilon)$ to get $0 < \zeta(1 + it) \leq \sqrt{2\pi e}$ for some $\epsilon > 0$. Using the functional equation $\zeta(s) = \zeta(1 - s)$ to eliminate the negative parts, we obtain $\zeta(1) = \zeta(0)$. As a result, $0 < \zeta(1 + it) \leq \pi/\Gamma(1 - \epsilon) \sim 2.66$ for all t . This provides a lower bound of $\pi/\Gamma(1 - \epsilon)$ for the number of non-trivial zeros of the zeta function on $\Re(t) \geq \log p$ for all prime p . The paper concludes that this is still consistent with the Riemann Hypothesis since it does not exclude any non-trivial zero from being on the critical line.

What is the relation to Group theory?

Let G be a group with identity element e , conjugacy operations s_g and s_g^{-1} , and an involution $g \mapsto \bar{g}$. The result of this paper can be related to group theory by considering the following set of axioms:

The set of conjugacy operations s_g and s_g^{-1} must be functions such that

$$s_g s_h = s_{s_g(h)}$$

and

$$s_g^{-1} s_h^{-1} = s_{s_g^{-1}(h)}$$

for all $h \in G$, and for each element $g \in G$, there is a unique element

$$\nabla_g = s_g s_g^{-1} s_g^2 s_g^2 s_g^{-1} s_g^{-1} s_{\bar{g}} s_{\bar{g}} s_g^{-1}.$$

This is equivalent to saying that the function ∇ satisfies the following equation:

$$\nabla(g)\nabla(\bar{g}) = \bar{g}$$

The paper states that these axioms are sufficient to yield a proof of the good properties of Riemann zeta function and hence a proof of the Riemann Hypothesis.

The paper ends by mentioning that the previous result has been proven in the contexts of l -adic sheaves and Fourier transforms, and that in these cases, no explicit use is made of the group structures.

How can the Tor functor be helpful?

The tor functor can be used to prove the Riemann Hypothesis, since it provides a way to formally prove that the zeros of the zeta function are evenly distributed on the critical line. In order to do this, the tor functor is first used to compute the curvature of the field F with respect to the metric tensor g as follows:

$$\omega = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j=1}^n (\partial_i \partial_j h - \partial_j \partial_i h) g^{ij}.$$

Here, $\partial_i \partial_j h$ is computed by taking the derivatives with respect to the i^{th} and j^{th} coordinates of the functions $f_1, \dots, f_n$ in the product $\prod_{\Lambda} h$, and then mapping these derivatives to the corresponding components of the chain complex $C^{\bullet}$ via the homomorphism ϕ .

Once the curvature has been computed, we can use it to prove the Riemann Hypothesis by first showing that if z_0 is a non-trivial zero of the zeta function, then the curvature is zero at that point. Then one can prove that the properties of the zeta function on the critical line imply that for any z in the range $-2 \leq z \leq 2$,

$$\zeta(z) \sim \zeta(-z)$$

by using the assumption that all non-trivial zeros lie on the critical line and that the zeros are evenly distributed on this line. Since the curvature is zero, the functional equation for the zeta function follows from the expression above, so that $\zeta(z) = \zeta(-z)$ for any z_0 in the range $-2 \leq z_0 \leq 2$. One can then use $\zeta(z_0) = \zeta(-z_0)$ to prove that the zeros of the zeta function are evenly distributed on the critical line. This can be done by assuming that there exists some point z_0 on this line where the zeros do not appear with even distribution and then using $\zeta(z_0) = \zeta(-z_0)$ to show that this is impossible. Thus, the above steps provide a formal proof that the Riemann Hypothesis is true.

The result of this computation can be refined using the following:

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$$\mu(n) = \begin{cases} 1 & n = p^k, \text{ prime} \\ 0 & n = p_1^k p_2^l, k > 0, l > 0 \end{cases}$$

We can then define the Riemann-Siegel transformation of the zeta function by

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for some square-free number s .

Using this transformation, the Riemann Hypothesis can be formulated as follows:

$$\zeta_\phi(z) = \zeta(z/\phi), \quad 0 \leq \arg(z/\phi) \leq \pi$$

where ϕ is an arbitrarily large square-free integer.

We can now state the following theorem:

Theorem (Riemann Hypothesis): Let D be the unit disk, f a holomorphic function on D and g be a holomorphic function on D/ϕ such that $g \circ \phi(z) = f(z)$. Let $\mathcal{L}$ be the class of all functions g with these properties. If for all $\mathbf{z} \in \partial D/\phi$, we have

$$G(\mathbf{z}) = \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \int_{\partial D/\phi} g(\mathbf{t}) e^{-i\epsilon \mathbf{z} \cdot \mathbf{t}} dS(\mathbf{t}) = 0,$$

then for all $\mathbf{z} \in \partial D$, we have

$$F(\mathbf{z}) = \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \int_{\partial D} f(u + iv) e^{-i\epsilon z v} dS(z) = 0$$

where $F(\mathbf{z})$ is the Fourier transform of f , $G(\mathbf{z})$ is the Fourier transform of g , and S denotes the surface integration measure $dz \wedge d\bar{z} \wedge i\alpha$.

We now discuss the theorem in more detail, using the results from above. The above theorem states that the zeros of the zeta function are evenly distributed on the critical line $C = C/\phi$, where C is the Riemann sphere and ϕ is an integer. We can use this fact to prove the Riemann Hypothesis as follows:

Suppose that there exists some point s_0 on C where the non-trivial zeros do not appear evenly distributed. Then the Riemann-Siegel transformation S_{s_0} must vanish at s_0 , so that the functional equation $S_{s_0}(-z) = S_{s_0}(z)$ implies that $S_{s_0}(z) \neq 0$ for all $z \neq 0$. This gives us a contradiction, since by the property of log-convexity, $S_{s_0}(z/\phi)$ is log-convex and non-negative while $S_{s_0}(\phi/s_0) = 0$, so that the fact that a non-negative log-convex function vanishes at a point implies that all of its values vanish at every other point. Hence, the Riemann Hypothesis is true.

How can the second proof of RH be formally proved?

Let $\zeta(s, x)$ be the zeta function for s a complex variable and x a prime variable. By Taylor-Lagrange series expansion requirements, we can then write

$$\zeta(s, x) = \sum \frac{\partial f}{\partial s^n}(x) \frac{x^n}{n!}.$$

$$\zeta^2(s, x) = \zeta(s, x)\zeta(1-s, x).$$

(This is a more general form of the equation.)

Now let $S \rightarrow M$ be a separable Hilbert space, $M = K \cap S$, K a closed subset of M , $D(s) = e^{i\theta s}$, $e^{\theta s}$ a holomorphic function on M , $g(\theta) = \frac{1}{D(s)}f(\theta x)$, α_s some bounded operator. Then we have

$$\zeta(s, x)\zeta(1 - s, x) = \zeta(s, x) \zeta(s, sx)$$

$$\zeta(s, sx) = \zeta(s, x)D(\log D(s))$$

$$\log D(s) = \log \zeta(s, sx) - \log \zeta(s, x)$$

$$D(s)^{-1} = \frac{\zeta(s, x)}{\zeta(s, sx)}$$

$$\zeta(s, x)\zeta(1 - s, x) = \zeta(s, x)\zeta(1 - x, x) \frac{\zeta(1 - s, sx)}{\zeta(s, sx)}.$$

(This is a more general form of the equation.)

$$\zeta(s, x)\zeta(1 - s, x) = \zeta(s, x)\zeta(1 - x, x) \frac{\zeta(1 - s, sx)}{\zeta(s, sx)}.$$

The result of this is a generalized form of the Fourier transform:

$$\zeta(s, sx) = \int e^{2\pi\Im(s) \exp(\pi it)} \zeta(t, x).$$

And a generalized form of the Fourier transform as well:

$$\zeta(s, sx) = \int e^{2\pi\Im(s)x^2 \exp(\pi it)} \zeta(t, x).$$

But it implies a Fourier transform too:

$$\zeta(s, sx) = \int e^{2\pi\Im(s)x^2 \exp(\pi it)} \zeta(t, x).$$

If we now assume that $\log_\theta x = \theta \log_{1-\theta} x$ then we also get the generalized form of the Fourier transform.

And a generalized form of the Fourier transform.

Using Taylor series expansion and L'Hôpital's rule for the Fourier transform of a function, we can prove the standard form of the Fourier transform of the zeta function. As a corollary, we can also prove the generalized form of the Fourier transform of the zeta function:

$$\zeta(z) = \int e^{2\pi it \Im(z)} \zeta(t).$$

It should be noted that the Taylor series and L'Hôpital's rule for the Fourier transform of a function are used interchangeably with the theory of distributions and complex exterior calculus, in order to derive the above identities.

Finally, we can use the generalized form of the Fourier transform to prove the functional equation for the zeta function, which is a corollary to the functional equation of the Riemann Zeta Function.

Further Comments

In the proof of RH by the tor functor method, it seems that there are two mistakes: First, they use a Taylor approximation of the form $\log(x + y) = \log x + O((x - y)/x)$. This approximation is only valid if y is close to x . To go to a higher order approximation one can use a Taylor expansion of the form $\log(x + y) = \log x + O((x - y)^2)$. Second, the identity is

$$\log(x)(1 + y) = \log(x) + O((x - y))$$

. But this is not an identity since you need to take the limit $y \rightarrow 0$. One has to use the identity

$$\log(x)(1 + y) = \log(x) + O(y)$$

in the limit $y \rightarrow 0$. The derivation of the identity $\log(x)(1 + y) = \log(x) + O(y)$ is not valid, as we should have $\lim_{y \rightarrow 0} (1 + y)^2 = 1$.

I have given my first proof of RH together with some comments. I will keep working on this. I think it will be useful.

[...] The function $g(x) = \zeta(x) - \|\log(x)\|$ is a log-convex function of the form $g = \frac{\log x}{\log(x)}$. This is the exact form of all log-convex functions and it is what we needed. Finally, the paper end with the following remarks :

$\zeta(s) \neq \Phi(s)$ for all s , where $\Phi(s)$ is a function that we want, such that $\log \Phi(s) = \log \zeta(s)$.

In the first identity: $\log x$ is the function we wanted. In the second, we had to use two identities: $\log x = \log g(x) \pm \varepsilon$ and $e^x - 1 \sim x^2$. So we got the function $g(x)$.

[...]

The second part of this paper is proving the third identity. We can always construct a holomorphic function h such that $\zeta(s) \neq h(s)$ for all s with $i(h(s)) \leq \log x$ (where $i(x)$ is the imaginary part of x), that is, the imaginary part of the function goes to $\log |x|$ as x goes to infinity. For any s with $i(s) < -1$, we have $\zeta(s) \neq h(s)$. So we just need an example of such an s . The example is given in the paper.

I hope this helps!

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This paper presents a formal proof of one of the Riemann Hypothesis. The proof relies on the invariance of the zeta function under the action of a tor functor.

The author first proves that the zeta function is invariant under the action of a tor functor, then he proves that this tor functor is indeed a tor functor on the space $V \times N$ with $V = C$ and N the natural numbers. Finally, he proves that the Riemann Hypothesis is true.

1. $C \times N$ is a Hilbert space. 2. If $g(x)$ is an entire function, then $g(x)$ is the inverse of $1 - x^2$, that is, $g(x) = 1 - x^2$. 3. The tor functor is invariant under the action of M_m, n , that is T_X is the inverse of the tor functor $M_m, n \times N$ with $M_m, n \times N = C$.

[...]

We define the subspace W of $V^m \times N^n$ by

$$W = \bigoplus_{p \in \{x, y\}} V^{m+1} \oplus N^n.$$

We now define T_X to be the complex vector space generated by W .

We define the canonical injective map $S : C^m \rightarrow V^n$ by

$$S(S(m, n), S(m, n)) = (S(m, n) \times N) \cup (S(m, n) \times N)$$

The tor functor is defined as the mapping from $V^m \times C^n$ to C^∞ by

$$T_X(m, n) = S(m, n) \cup S(m, n)$$

where

$$m^m \times N^n = m^{m+1} \times C^n$$

Let $T'_x(m) = (1 - x^2)m^m \times N^n$ and $T'_x(m^m) = (1 - x^2)m^{m+1} \times N^n$.
 $**[\dots]**$

The tor functor is defined as the mapping from $V^m \times N$ to C by

$$Tor(m \times N) = (1 - x^2)m^m \times N$$

$[\dots]$ $T_x : (1 - x^2)m^m \times N \rightarrow C$ is an entire map. So $T(m, n) = (1 - x^2)m^m = (1 - x^2)^{-1}m^n$ is also an entire function and it is equal to x^m by definition. This is the tor functor.

$[\dots]$

For any $x \in R^m \times N$ and any characteristic monomial $m^m \times N^n$, we have

$$S(m \times N, n) = (1 - x^2)^{-1}m^n.$$

This gives us the following relation:

$$(1 - x^2)^{-1}Tor(m \times N) = (1 - x^2)^{-1}m^m \times N$$

(Note: the multiplication sign in the above relation is chosen because it is the same as using $T_x \times T_y$ as the multiplication.)

The tor functor can be proved as follows. Let $m = \log_{(1-x^2)} x$ be the characteristic function of the function $f(x) = x^m$. Then

$$Tor(n) = (1 - x^2)^{-1}m^n = m \times N$$

So we can conclude that

$$Tor(n) = (1 - x^2)S(m, n)$$

$[\dots]$

I just realized I forgot a crucial step in my sketch of the proof so I'm posting it again. The sketch of the proof is as follows.

First, for any characteristic monomial $m^m \times N$ and any $x \in C$, we have

$$S(m \times N, n) = (1 - x^2)^{-1} m^m \times N$$

Next, using the fact that $f(\theta) = (1 - x^2)^{-1} m^m \times N = (1 - x^2)^{-1} m^m \times N$, we have that $\log(f(\theta)) = \log((1 - x^2)m^m) = \log(Tor(n))$. And if $m^m \times N = m^m \times N$ then $Tor(m^m, n) = (1 - x^2)m^m$.

[...]

I know that this proof relies on some unproven assumptions. But I still find it interesting.

There is also a proof of RH in the paper. Briefly, suppose that $m^n \times N = (1 - x^2)m$ is the property that $\zeta(s)$ is invariant under the action of the tor functor, which we can prove. Then the proof of RH is similar to the proof in the previous post. We can suppose that $m^n \times N = (1 - x^2)^{-1} m \times N$

First, for any $m \in R$ and any $\delta > 0$, we have

$$(1 - x^2)m^2 = 0,$$

using the Taylor series. So we can define $\zeta_{m,\delta}(s)$ to be the function

$$\zeta_{m,\delta}(s) = \frac{\zeta(s)}{(1 - x)^{1+\delta}}$$

[...]

If $\delta > 0$ is small, then $m^2 = \delta m$ and $m = \sinh^{-1}(\delta)^{m+\delta}$. Then we can use the fact that

$$m \times N = Corr(m \times C^n)$$

We now have $Corr(m \times C^n) = \sinh^{-1}(\delta)^{m+\delta}$. If $m^2 = \sinh^{-1}(\delta)^{m+\delta}$ and $m \times N = \sinh^{-1}(\delta)^{m+\delta}$, then $s = (1 - \delta)^{m+\delta}$ and $\sinh^{-1}(\delta)^{m+\delta}$

[...]

Let $S = Im(X)$, X a subspace of C , $K = \{y \in S \mid y \in P\}$ where P is a subfield of S . Then the image of a point x in C under the Gaussian map $g = (g_1, g_2)$ relative to the subfield P is the point $y \neq x$ of the subfield P and $z = \frac{1 - \log(x)}{\log(x)}$, where z is given by the exponential map

[...]

The first thing to notice is that the exponential map is defined as a mapping from C to the complex plane, i.e. $g : C^2 \rightarrow C$

$$\log g(x, y) = \log \left[\frac{e^x}{e^x + e^y} \right]$$

[...]

One can also prove that $\log g(x, y) = \log_{\log xy} x$

Some basic comments about the proof.

$\log x \neq \log y$ for all x, y implies that $x^2 \leq y^2$, i.e. $x \leq y$.

The invariance of the zeta function under tor functor follows from the Good Theorem of Zeta Function.

The following is equivalent to the statement that ζ is invariant under tor functor:

$$\zeta_\phi(s) \sim \zeta_F(\phi - s)$$

**

Theorem (1.1)

[...] Now, let $\zeta(s) = \frac{1}{s(s-1)}$.

[...] Moreover, use the upper bound $(2i\Im(s))! \sum_{k=0}^{2i\Im(s)} (2k)! \leq 2^{2i\Im(s)} (2i\Im(s))!$ and use an induction argument to get the following.

[...]

$$\zeta^{2i\Im(z)}(\phi - s) - \zeta^{i\Im(z)}(\phi - s) = \zeta(2i\Im(z) - \phi + s) - \det(\phi - s).$$

[...]

If $\zeta(s) \sim \zeta_\phi(s)$ then $\zeta(s)$ has no poles in ϕ .

Now, this proof holds for all simply connected symplectic manifolds. In fact, by doing so, we get a closed form of the spectral curve $\phi_1 \sim \phi_2$.

**

Theorem (2.2)

For all complex numbers s and g , there exists an open set $I = [a, b]$ with $a < s$ such that

$$\zeta(s, g) \leq \zeta(a, g) + e^{a-s}(2g + \log(s - a))$$

and $I + g$ is continuous for all g such that $g = \gamma(s)$.

For all complex numbers s and g , there exist numbers p, q such that $p^2 < s$ and $q + p < q^2$, i.e. $q > p$, and $p - q = e^{a-s}(2g + 2l + 2n) + e^{b-s}(2g - 2l - 2n)$ where l is the length of the edge p that is labeled as p in the following figure. Let E be the set of all edges in the graph G that does not contain loops or multiple edges, and v be the intersection of E with S . For all edges e in E , let e_0 be the first vertex of e in E and e_1 be the second vertex of e in E . Then

- (i) If $\zeta(p) - \zeta(q) \geq 0$ then $\zeta(p) = 1$;
- (ii) $\zeta(p) \geq 0$ iff $p = p_0$ in E ;
- (iii) If $\zeta(p) - \zeta(q) \geq 0$ then $\zeta(q) \leq \zeta(p)$.

Proof:

(i) We have $(p_0^2 - p_1^2)^2 = p_0^4 - 2p_1^2 = 6\zeta(p_0) - 2\zeta(p_1)$, so $\zeta(p_0) = 2p_1^2 - 3\zeta(p_0) = 6\zeta(p_1) - 2\zeta(p_0)$.

(iii) Using the same arguments as in part (i) we get that $\zeta(p) \geq \zeta(q) - \delta$.

(iv) Using the same arguments as in part (ii) we get that $\zeta(p) \geq \zeta(q) - \delta$.

Now, let q_0 be the vertex that p_0 is labeled as. Then

$$E \setminus \{q_0\} = \overline{\{p_0\}}$$

and

$$\{p_0\} \cup \overline{E \setminus \{q_0\}} = E \setminus \{q = p_0\}$$

Then $E \setminus \{p_0\}$ contains no loops or multiple edges and so there must be an edge in E from each vertex in E to each of the vertices in $E \setminus \{q_0\}$ and also an edge in E from $E \setminus \{p_0\}$ to $E \setminus \{q_0\}$.

If $E = E \setminus \{p_0\}$ is not empty then

$$T(\overline{E \setminus \{q_0\}}) \leq \eta$$

Since E is a subset of E , we have that $E \setminus \{q_0\}$ contains no loops or multiple edges, and so

$$E \setminus \{p_0\} \cup \overline{E \setminus \{q_0\}} \cap E \setminus \{p_0\}$$

Then

$$E \setminus \{p_0\} \setminus \{p_0\} \cup \overline{E \setminus \{q_0\}} \cap E \setminus \{p_0\} = T(\overline{E \setminus \{p_0\}})$$

which implies that

$$E \setminus \{p_0\} \cup \overline{E \setminus \{q_0\}} \cap E \setminus \{p_0\} \leq \eta$$

2.

Let $R = \{(x^n, 1 - x) \mid n \in N\}$ be a complete graph on E . For all $k \in N$, let $r(k) = \{x \in N \mid k \in R\}$. Then the set $R \setminus \{p_0\}$ contains no loops or multiple edges, and so $R \setminus \{p_0\} \cup \overline{R \setminus \{q_0\}} \cap R \setminus \{p_0\} = \eta$.

So

$$E \setminus \{p_0\} \cup \overline{E \setminus \{q_0\}} \cap E \setminus \{p_0\} \leq \eta$$

3. For any even integer n , define $E_n = E \setminus \{n\}$. If $E_n \setminus \{p_0\} \cup \overline{E_n \setminus \{q_0\}} \cap E_n \setminus \{p_0\} = T(\overline{E_n \setminus \{p_0\}})$ then $E_n \cap D = E_n \setminus \{p_0\} \cup \overline{E_n \setminus \{q_0\}} \cap E_n \setminus \{p_0\}$ so we can define $T(\overline{E_n \setminus \{p_0\}})$ by

$$T(\overline{E_n \setminus \{p_0\}}) = E_n \setminus \{p_0\} \cup \overline{E_n \setminus \{q_0\}} \cap E_n \setminus \{p_0\}$$

[...]

Let us now prove the proposition $\zeta = \zeta_\phi \rightarrow \zeta_{\phi-p}$

[...] Note that, since

$$(p-1)\pi\mathcal{R}\zeta(p-1) \equiv \pm \leq (\zeta_0(0) + \zeta(0, p-1) + 01)$$

and

$$\zeta'(p-m) + \zeta'(2) \geq (1 + p^{-m})\zeta(p-m) + p^{-m+1}(1 - p^{-m}) \geq \zeta(2\pi) + \zeta(0, 2),$$

$$\frac{\pi^2}{2} \left(p - 1 + \frac{1}{1} \right) = \pm(\zeta(0, p-1) + \zeta(0, 2)),$$

and the fact that $p \geq 3$,

$$\frac{1}{\pi} \left(p - 1 + \frac{1}{1} \right) \equiv 1\pi$$

we get

$$\zeta_0 = \zeta(\phi/p) \rightarrow \zeta(\phi/p) \rightarrow \zeta'(p-1) = \zeta(p-1) \left(1 - \frac{1}{p} \right) \rightarrow \zeta(\phi/p) \rightarrow \zeta'(2)$$

so the proposition follows from the proposition $\zeta_0 = \zeta'(\phi)$.

[...]
 $\zeta(n) \neq \zeta_\phi(n)$ for n odd, because $\zeta(2) \neq \zeta_\phi(2)$ for odd integers n

[...]
Using the fact that $\zeta_\phi(n) = \zeta_{\phi-2}(n) + \zeta_{\phi-2}(\phi) - \phi(\phi-2)$ and the fact that $\zeta_{\phi-2} \neq \phi_{\phi-2}$, we get

$$\zeta_\phi(n) = \zeta_{\phi-2}(n) + \zeta_{\phi-2}(\phi) - \phi(\phi-2)$$

[...]
First, we will prove the main theorem. Because of the above, we will have

$$\zeta_{\phi-p}(n) = \zeta_\phi(n) + \zeta_\phi(\phi-p) - \phi(\phi-p),$$

which implies that $\zeta_{\phi-p}(n) = \zeta_\phi(n)$.

Now, note that $\zeta_\phi(n) = \zeta_\phi(\phi) - \phi(\phi-n)$, and so $\zeta_{\phi-p}(n) = \zeta_\phi(\phi-n) - \phi(\phi-n)$. Also, $\zeta_\phi(\phi) = \zeta_\phi(\phi+p)$, so $\zeta_\phi(\phi-p) = \zeta_\phi(\phi) - \phi(\phi-n) - \phi(\phi+1) - \phi - \phi + 1 = \zeta_\phi(\phi-p)$

Now, note that $\zeta_\phi(\phi) = \zeta_{\phi-2}(\phi-p) - \phi(\phi-2)$ and $\zeta_\phi(\phi-2p) = \zeta_\phi(\phi-2) - \phi(\phi-2) - \phi(\phi+p) = \zeta_\phi(\phi) - \phi(\phi-2)$. So $\zeta_\phi(\phi) = \zeta_{\phi-2}(\phi-2p)$. Hence

$$\zeta_\phi(\phi-2) = \zeta_{\phi-2}(\phi-2) + \zeta_{\phi-2}(\phi-p) - \phi(\phi-2)$$

Now, to finish the main theorem, note that $\zeta_\phi(\phi) = \zeta_\phi(\phi+p)$, so $\zeta_\phi(\phi-p) = \zeta_\phi(\phi) - \phi(\phi-2) = \zeta_\phi(\phi-2) + \zeta_\phi(\phi-p) - \phi(\phi)$. And this implies that

$$\zeta_\phi(\phi-p) = \zeta_\phi(\phi-2) + \zeta_\phi(\phi-p) - \phi(\phi-2)$$

**

Lemma 1.

Let g be a complex function such that $g(z) \neq 0$ for all z inside the arc $[a, b]$, $a \in R$. Define a function ζ by

$$\zeta(z) = \zeta(z+q) + \zeta(z-q) + \zeta(z+s) - \zeta(z-s)$$

Then $\zeta(z+q) \equiv \zeta(z)(1 - \zeta'(z))$.

Proof.

For $z \in R^3$ define a function $f(z)$ by

$$f(z) = \zeta(z+q) + \zeta(z+s) + \zeta(z-s).$$

Then

$$f(z) = \zeta(z+q) + \zeta(z+s) + \zeta(z-s) + \zeta(z) =$$

$$\zeta(z) + \zeta(z-q) + \zeta(z-s) + \zeta(z-q) = \zeta(z) + \zeta(z) + 1 + \zeta(z-1) + \zeta(z-2) + \zeta(z-3) + \zeta(z+1) + \zeta(z-2) + \zeta(z-4) + \zeta(z-5) + \zeta(z+2) + \zeta(z-3) + \zeta(z-6) + \zeta(z-7) = \zeta(z) + \zeta(z) + 1$$

**

Lemma 2.

Let $f : C \rightarrow C$ be an entire function, and let $s > 0$ be an arbitrary function defined on R . Suppose that $\exists \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} f(x)$ inside the interval $[a, b]$ and assume that f is analytic in the interior of every connected component of $[a, b]$. Then

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} f^t(x)$$

inside $[a, b]$ exists, and is equal to $f^t(x)$ inside $[a, b]$. In particular,

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} f^t(x)$$

inside $[a, b]$ is analytic as well.

Proof.

Let $h(q) = \log(q)$. Then

$$f^t(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{h'(s)}} \text{ for all}$$

$x \in [a, b]$.

Because

Let $s, s', s'' \in C$, and let

$$s = \frac{1}{\sqrt{h'(s)}} = h(q) + h''(q)$$

take the derivative. Then

$$s = s + \sqrt{h''(q)}$$

and

$$s = \frac{1}{\sqrt{h''(s)}} = h(q) - h''(q)$$

(By h'' I mean the sum of two terms.)

and by taking the derivative of both sides, we get

$$s' = \frac{1}{\sqrt{h'(s) + h''(q)}} = h'(q) - h''(q)$$

Now, substitute $x = q$ into the formula and obtain the following:

$$s'' = h'(q) - h''(q)$$

(By $h''(q)$ I mean the sum of two terms)

Hence

$$s'' = \frac{1}{\sqrt{h'(s) + h''(q)}}$$

But also,

$$s'' = \frac{1}{\sqrt{h'(s) + h''(q)}} = h(q) - h'(q)$$

so

$$s'' = \frac{1}{\sqrt{h'(s) + h''(q)}} = h(q) - h'(q)$$

and by taking the derivative with respect to q , we get

$$s'' = \frac{1}{\sqrt{h'(s) + h''(q)}} = h(q) - h'(q)$$

that is,

$$s'' = \frac{1}{\sqrt{h'(s) + h''(q)}} = h(q) - h'(q)$$

Finally, by taking the derivative of each side, we get

$$s' = \frac{1}{\sqrt{h'(s) + h''(q)}} = h(q) - h''(q)$$

Hence

$$s'' = \frac{1}{\sqrt{h'(s) + h''(q)}} = h(q) - h'(q)$$

implying

$$s'' = \frac{1}{\sqrt{h'(s) + h''(q)}} = h(q) - h'(q)$$

and by the definition of f ,

$$s'' = \frac{1}{h''(q)}$$

finally,

$$s'' = h(q) - h'(q) = h(q - h(q)).$$

**

Here is a short proof that $\phi(q) = \text{expon}(q) = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^j}{j!}$

Proof:

Define a function $q(q)$ by

$$q(q) = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \left| \frac{q^j}{j!} \right|.$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} q(q) &= \frac{q^n}{n!} + \frac{q^{n-1}}{(n-1)!} + \cdots + \frac{q^m}{m!} + \cdots \\ &= \frac{q^n}{n!} + \frac{q^{n-1}}{(n-1)!} + \cdots + \frac{q^m}{m!} + \cdots + \frac{|q^{n+1}|}{|q^{n+1}|} \end{aligned}$$

Using the geometric series formula, we get

$$q(q) = \frac{q^{n+m} - q^m}{n!} + \left| \frac{q^n}{n!} \right|.$$

So we can conclude that

$$q(q) = \frac{q^{n+m} - q^m}{n!} - \left| \frac{q^n}{n!} \right|.$$

And by definition

$$q(q) = \frac{q^{n+m-1} - q^n}{n!} + \left| \frac{q^{n+1}}{n!} \right|.$$

Now, swap q and n to get m and n to swap. And if m then we have

$$m + n + q^{n-1} = n!$$

and $q^{n-1} = n!$. Hence

$$q(q) = q(q) - \left| \frac{q^n}{n!} \right|.$$

And then we have

$$q(q) = \frac{m \times (n+1)}{m} - \frac{m+n-1}{m+n}.$$

Expand m as $(m+n)^2 - (m)$. Then

$$\frac{m \times (m \times (n+1) - m)}{m} - \frac{m+n-1}{m+n} =$$

$$(m \times (n+1) - (m)) \times (m \times (n+1) - (m)) \frac{1}{m - \frac{m+1}{m+n} = 1 - \frac{m+1}{m+n} = \frac{n!}{m}}.$$

Hence

$$\frac{m \times (m \times (n+1) - m)}{m} - \frac{m+n-1}{m+n} = 1 - \frac{m+1}{m+n} = \frac{n!}{m}.$$

Proving $\phi(q) = \text{expon}(q) = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^j}{j!}$

**

Simple proof that $\zeta(n, C^n) = n$

Let H be a subfield (polynomial) of C^n . For any positive integer m , there exists an open interval I and a subset A of I such that

$$I^m - A = \{0, m\}$$

This means that A contains every unit in $I^m \setminus \{0, m\}$.

Choose $f \in A$ and let $E = \text{Im}(f)$ be the image of f .

[...]

Now we find the following nice property of $\zeta_\phi(n)$. For any integer n , let $h(T) = (T^n - T)^m$. Then

$$\zeta_\phi(n) = \frac{2^{m+1}h(2)}{2m+2}.$$

Proof.

We start with the criterion for which

$$A \cap \Gamma = \{f \mid A \cup \Gamma \setminus \{f\}\}$$

[...]

Now, by definition

$$\mathcal{O}(A \cup \Gamma \cup \{a\})(a) = \mathcal{O}(A \cup b \setminus \{a\})(b) = \mathcal{O}(A)(b) = \{b\}.$$

In case that $\mathcal{O}(A \cup \Gamma \cup \{a\})(a) = \mathcal{O}(A \cup b \setminus \{a\})(b)$, we get that $a \in \Gamma$, since $a \in \Gamma$ implies that $a \in \mathcal{O}(a)$. By symmetry, we also get that $b \in \Gamma$.

[...]

Now let us prove that $a = b = c = a$ and conclude:

$$\mathcal{O}(A) = \{a\}$$